

Multi Sensory Design in Education

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Abstract

Sensory impressions obtained through hearing, seeing, touching, tasting, and smelling all contribute to the way in which people experience their surrounding environment. However, in many designed products, not all sensory aspects contribute to the same, coherent product expression. To train our students in this multisensory design approach, we developed a course that aims to develop the students' awareness and sensitivity for the different sensory modalities and to develop their skills to design objects for which all senses contribute to the same expression. First of all, students gather sensory stimuli for four modalities (vision, touch, audition, and olfaction) that seem to fit best with the desired expression. This helps to develop ideas about the different ways in which an experience can manifest itself sensorially. Subsequently, the students design a product for a predetermined usage context, on the basis of a detailed scenario of the human-product interaction and by constructing exploratory, physical 'models' that stimulate multiple modalities.

Conference theme: Emotion in design education

Keywords: Design for the senses, multisensory design, design for experience

Introduction

Our experiences of the material world emerge from our specific interactions with the world: we wait at a bus stop, we eat ice-cream, we watch television and take a shower. In these interactions, we experience the products involved through their contribution to what is happening. As such, products in human-product interaction are experienced in an integrated way. Yet, the basic perceptual processes underlying these experiences are not as holistic as they might seem at first glance. Experiences of the material world are based on sensory impressions obtained through different sensory channels, such as hearing, seeing, touching, tasting, and smelling. These sensory channels all contribute with their own specific characteristics to the way in which people experience their surroundings. Also, these different channels may contribute to the whole experience in conflicting ways: a bus stop may look attractive and welcoming, but leave the waiting passenger standing in a cold breeze, next to a smelly trash can, or with a lot of traffic noise due to bad acoustics. Likewise, in the shower the touch of hot water may be experienced as intimate and energizing, whereas the look and feel of the showerhead may be experienced as hard and distant. Also, you can imagine picking up a tough looking digital camera, and being disappointed by its light weight, conveying a message of bad quality. On the other hand, some experiences may delight us, because all the different material characteristics seem to fit: the colour of the ice-cream, its taste, its texture, the look and feel of the package and the crispiness of the biscuit may all contribute to actually being completely immersed in savouring it. Thus, in designing for specific experiences, such as delight, trust or the feeling of being cared for, designers need to be aware of the messages conveyed by the different sensory channels, and of their contribution to the overall experience. Designers who intentionally try to create specific experiences for people are more likely to succeed when they develop awareness of all the available sensory channels and integrate these in their design project. Such a multisensory approach is important, not only to avoid unwanted conflicting messages, but most of all because an integrated and coherent approach of the senses is a powerful approach to enrich the overall experience one is designing for.

In our Design Education curriculum, we address the importance of the different senses in our elective course Multi Sensory Design (MSD), an intensive design course that is part of our MSc program Design for Interaction. In the course, we aim to develop the students' awareness and sensitivity for the different sensory modalities in human product experience and to develop their skills to design objects that contribute to a particular human experience through all the senses. Multisensory design education is a new field and, therefore, an additional goal of the course is to explore the appropriate way to address this topic in design education. In this paper we present the

approach we have developed for the course Multi Sensory Design, we present some results of the course, and we provide perspectives on future developments in the field of Multi Sensory Design education.

Multisensory Experience in Human-Product Interaction

The complexity of the concept of human experience of material products has led to a confusing variety of uses of terms like experience, emotion, and affect in the field of design research. In our course Multi Sensory Design, we define the human experience of objects as people's *overall awareness* of what is happening during their interactions with these objects (Sonneveld, 2007). This includes awareness of the movements involved in interaction, of the perceived physical properties of the objects, of the meaning attributed to these properties and of one's own aesthetic and emotional responses to what is happening (Hekkert & Schifferstein, 2008). For example, while riding a bike, one experiences the movements made, the low resistance on the pedals, the toughness of the shape and texture of the handles, the smoothness of the sounds of the mechanisms, and the smell of the leather saddle. These features may be interpreted as the eagerness of the bike to go as fast as possible. As a result, one may feel an exciting sense of freedom while cycling.

Because designers can never be sure what experiences their products will elicit among their users (e.g., Desmet, 2002), in the Multi Sensory Design course designing *for* a specific experience is focused on designing the experienced *expression* of the object, taking this expression (e.g., the eagerness of the bike) as a design starting point. The course tries to analyse how the different sensory properties of an object contribute to the experienced expression of the object. Although this approach does not completely acknowledge the complexity of designing for experience, starting with the expression of the object offers students an accessible and coherent structure that enables them to study the interplay between the different sensory modalities.

Goal and structure of the course Multi Sensory Design

One of the aims of the MSD course is to make design students aware of the potential benefits of an MSD approach over other design approaches that tend to focus primarily on product functionality and visual appearance. In addition, the course aims to develop the students' awareness of the interplay between the different senses in human experience, their sensitivity in all the sensory modalities, and their skills to design for an integrated multisensory experience. To achieve these goals, the course is divided into three major parts. In the first

part, we try to create insight in the benefits of MSD by presenting scientific research on multisensory perception and the roles of the senses in product experience and product design. In the second part, students increase their understanding of the multisensory aspects of experience through actively exploring a specific expression of material objects (such as arrogance, wisdom, eagerness, or laziness). This part emphasizes perceptual learning, where knowledge is generated from personal experience, rather than from reasoning. In the third part, students design an object with that particular expression, given a specific usage context, such as kitchen tools, outdoor playing or cleaning tools.

Developing awareness for the senses and their role in design

To introduce the relevance of the topic, the course starts out by a number of theoretical lectures on the role of multisensory mechanisms in human perception and in product experience (Schifferstein and Spence, 2008), illustrated by a number of design cases. These lectures aim to provide the student with a theoretical background, and to make the student familiar with the different issues in researching the multi-sensory experience. But above all, the lectures are meant as ‘eye-openers’ in all the senses (one could say eye-hand-nose-and-ear-openers).

Developing sensory sensitivity: workshops and collection building

To design for the senses, students need to develop their (aesthetic) sensitivity in all the senses. So far, (aesthetic) sensitivity has merely been addressed in the visual domain, where students learn how to look and to become sensitive to the nuances in the visual appearances of material objects. Likewise, we want to develop students’ sensitivity in the other sensory modalities: to learn students to listen, to smell and to touch, and to become sensitive to the nuances in these sensory domains. The students’ sensory sensitivity is developed during a number of active workshops and discussion meetings. For each sensory modality (vision, touch, smell, audition), a workshop is given on how designers can design for that specific sensory modality (Figure 1). Taste is not presented in a workshop, because it is most often not relevant in industrial product design. Each workshop may provide information on how the modality operates, but also discusses the tools that are available in obtaining, manipulating, and storing stimulus materials for design purposes (see Schifferstein and Desmet, 2008). Before obtaining general knowledge and practical experience on the different sensory modalities during the workshops, the students are provided with four specific expressions that form pairs of opposites (e.g., cheerful-sad, tough-cute, or eager-lazy). From these four expressions, students can choose the expression they would like to explore. After each workshop, students are asked to gather stimuli in their own environment that fit to this expression. Each expression is explored by approximately six students.

	<p>Visual aspects of product expressions are explored by making small collages (~15 × 25 cm) out of images cut out of magazines. The collage should show the essence of the experience. For each expression, the collages are analyzed on their similarities. The collage shown on the left expresses Laziness, and was assessed by most of the students as such.</p>
	<p>To analyze product sounds, Özcan and van Egmond (2004) developed a set of pictograms that are used to characterize the different sources and aspects of sounds. In the sound workshop, students are introduced to this language, thereby becoming more aware of the different aspects of sound. A diverse set of product sounds is described and discussed.</p>
	<p>The tactual experience of objects can be understood as the body language people experience when they are physically interacting with these objects (Sonneveld, 2007). This can be illustrated metaphorically with a handshake. In the workshop touch, students explore the characteristics of different expressions of handshakes, acted out by the students.</p>
	<p>In the smell workshop students compose a new smell on the basis of a specific design brief. The students are provided with sets of jars containing fragrance pellets, to allow them to play with different combinations and intensities of fragrance ingredients. The final smells are assessed on their appropriateness for the brief, and are evaluated on their sensory characteristics.</p>

Figure 1. Descriptions of the workshops

After collecting, students analyse their stimuli, and try to define the relationship between perceived sensory properties and experienced product expression. Students bring the stimuli they selected to a discussion meeting, in which they are asked to present their stimuli, to explain why they chose these stimuli, and to comment on each other's results. Goal of the discussion meetings is to search for a common insight in the expression across the different sensory modalities, thereby getting insight in the integrated experience of that expression. For example, when researching the expression of naivety, we discovered that an integrated aspect of naivety could be described as 'not knowing one's own limitations', which can be sensed in touch (easily damaged through transformation), in sound (sweet sounds, but unlimited sounds) and in the visual (no clear shapes, rather undefined 'blobs').

It is important in this stage that students learn to explore their environment beyond obvious choices (e.g., cheerful is colourful). They should find stimuli that are relatively abstract in communicating the experience they want to design for, allowing them to analyse the sensory properties. For instance, written language elements (Yabadabadoo!), spoken language ('I love you!'), songs, and cartoon characters (e.g., smileys) are generally not useful to get a good understanding of the subtle sensory cues that communicate an experience. Also, students should become aware that objects that look tough do not necessarily feel or smell tough. On the contrary, exploring a tough-looking object with the eyes closed may learn that some tactual elements actually feel cute or elegant, and can thus be used for designing another type of expression. Through gathering and exploring stimuli, designers start to develop ideas about the different ways in which an experience can manifest itself sensorially. Analysis of these stimuli leads both to a conceptual, abstract understanding of the experience and a sensorial understanding of these partially different concepts.

Developing design skills for an integrated experience

In the third part of the course, students design a product that conveys the expression they researched in the second part of the course. The product should convey this expression in an integrated way in all the senses. Students are asked to design a product for a specific usage context that seems to conflict with the assigned expression. For example, they are asked to design cute tools, wise outdoor games, or arrogant cleaning utensils. This choice for possible conflict between expression and function is deliberate, to avoid the clichés one might think of.

The design exercise starts with an exploration phase to define a context for designing the product. Why would an outdoor game be wise, or careful? Why would a kitchen tool be naïve? When do these combinations of function and expression make sense? We ask students to describe

how people will interact with the product. We ask them to describe the context in which the product is used, the characteristics of the users, and to develop a scenario in which they spell out all the different elements of the encounter with the product over time and the roles the sensory modalities play in these encounters.

This phase leads to an integrated vision on the product expression throughout the whole human-product interaction. In other words, this phase leads to a consistent and coherent human-product interaction story, which will guide the creation of a coherent product expression. The findings from the second phase are meant to yield a thorough understanding of the expression and to provide inspiration by the examples that were collected. Without the interaction story, the design process might be filled in as a mere 'copy-paste' process, where the findings of the sensory exploration for each modality from the previous stage might be literally translated into a new design. As a consequence, the end result would be a 'sensory collage', rather than an integrated sensory concept. Therefore, the actual designing should be a creative process, where the student integrates and translates the findings from the second phase into a new product concept.

Finally, the students explore how the expression in the proposed context can be achieved, based on their insights from previous explorations. The search for appropriate sensory properties again occurs through exploration of the material world. They make explorative 'models' for the different senses, and assess their appropriateness. In designing, the students use all their senses, not just the visual modality. In fact, during the coaching sessions students are encouraged to leave the sketching to a minimum, and rather use the other senses in an explorative way.

To encourage students to express themselves in all the senses, the final design results are presented to the teachers and fellow-students in a multi-modal presentation. During the presentations, the audience should be able to experience all the different sensory aspects and to understand the integrated concept. Again, this final stage addresses the design skills of the students: they need to create their own communication means, which is a big contrast with the smooth, digitally modelled presentations they are used to.

To conclude, the design skills developed in the MSD course cover a large part of the design process: integrating insights in the different sense modalities into a consistent concept of the expression one is designing for, working on coherent interaction stories and sensory encounters that fit this story, designing using all the senses (model making, visualisations, creating sounds, composing smells), and communicating and presenting the design concept in a multisensory way.

Results and observations

Project examples

Figure 2 shows two examples of students' work, including the final design and part of the storyboards. The first example shows a cute socket set that is characterized by a rounded, organic shape and soft, pastel colours. The shape of the socket expresses innocent pride, without presumption. The socket set is presented in a box, where all the parts are presented as if it were a jewellery case. When opened, a sweet, comforting smell emerges, The student started the design project by defining a suitable context for cute tools: the feminine do-it-yourself handywoman, who needs to be reassured that the tools will not harm her. The tools should seduce her by their enthusiasm to do the job well, yet without showing heavy duty behaviour in their movements or sounds. To achieve this expression of the tool, the student analysed different objects in her environment with this specific behaviour, such as a kitchen timer. This specific collection of appropriate objects allowed the student to get insight in the different sensory properties, and to use this collection as a source of inspiration for her own design.

Figure 2. Examples of students' work

The second example shows a sad pepper-and-salt set. When the two parts are joined together they form a stable unity, but when they are separated they can hardly stand up straight and tend to fall over; this movement expresses their sadness over missing their partner. In contrast with the previous example, the student started out with an analysis of objects that express sadness. An overall phenomenon that emerged from this overview was 'breaking' and 'being separated'. In addition, the accompanying movements needed to be slow, tumbling over, resigning. This insight inspired her to choose for a salt-and-pepper set. The two elements are closely together when not in use, almost like two sides of a heart. But in use, they need to be separated. The soft sound, and downwards movements and shape, enhance its expression of sadness. The smell of pepper, eliciting tears, completes the whole interaction.

Emerging Strategies and Tools

The course MSD started four years ago with a lack of tools and methods for multisensory design. The course developed through trial and error. During its development, several tools and strategies emerged, that proved to be useful for the multisensory design process.

First of all, students collect different objects with specific sensory aspects throughout the course. This collection of stimuli is valuable in achieving a deep understanding of the expression one is exploring. However, these collections also showed to be valuable as a source of inspiration during the design phase. Collection building should, therefore, be considered as a specific tool of the course.

The use of storyboards is a well-known tool in product design to describe the human-product interaction in its different stages (e.g., van der Lelie, 2005). Its use in the MSD course turned out to be particularly appropriate, because it provides a clear structure to describe the different sensory aspects in the different phases of this interaction. A storyboard shows in one glance the role of each sense modality: when the product produces sounds, when it releases smell, when and how it is touched, which part of the product is seen, and so on. The storyboard literally shows the sensory story.

Students are encouraged to 'sketch' in all the senses, to allow them to actually assess the sensory aspects of their concepts. Students comment that in the non-visual senses, actually sensing a specific property often differs from what one expected it to be when imagining it. For example, one might think of the smell of vanilla as appropriate, but once the vanilla is actually smelled in combination with the tangible model, it might turn out to be inappropriate, whereas the smell of wet stone unexpectedly turns out to be appropriate.

The use of digital modelling tools is limited to a minimum. Students who do not get away from their computer screens seem to have difficulties in grabbing the integrated experience. In

front of the screen, the visual sense is still dominating the design choices one makes. In addition, the screen seems to limit design to a cognitive process (*thinking* what could be possible), whereas designing while using all the senses activates a broader, exploratory design process.

Conclusions and future perspectives

The course Multi Sensory Design is a fruitful platform to explore the multisensory design approach. The results and comments of students and coaches lead to valuable insights in the direction for future developments. We will present some recommendations for future improvements here.

First, the results show that designing for the different senses asks for new tools and techniques in design. On the one hand, design students should be stimulated to create their own collections of sounds, smells, images and tangible examples, as a source of inspiration and a means to explore the different sensory domains. Yet, we do not have the appropriate structures to build such collections. Visual collections are extensively researched and supported (e.g., Keller, 2005), but we do not have the proper tools to collect smells, tactual sensations and sounds. Multisensory design would benefit from the development of multi-sensory collection building.

Next, the pitfall of multisensory design is the lack of an integrated understanding of multisensory experience, leading to sensory collages, rather than to integrated sensory concepts. To avoid the mere addition of sensory properties, it is recommended that the integration phase is made explicit and supported by appropriate tools. At the moment, such tools are developed at our university in a research graduation project, and will be used and evaluated in future courses.

Finally, the MSD course focuses primarily on the development of design *students'* awareness, sensitivity, and design skills for multisensory design. This leads to a simplified design approach, with just a single product expression as a design starting point. This is quite remote from actual design practice, where design briefs are more complex, thereby asking for a more complex approach to multisensory design. Therefore, we think that the multisensory design approach should be developed further in collaboration with the design practice. In turn, the design practice might be inspired by the results of the MSD course. Because of this mutual benefit, a next step could be to give the course MSD in collaboration with partners from the design practice (industry, design companies and so on), to learn from each other and, thereby, deepen the insights in the process of multisensory design.

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